

Review Paper

Method Development and Validation of Simultaneous Estimation of Oxycodone and Acetaminophen in Bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms by RP-HPLC Method

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ABSTRACT

A rapid, sensitive, and accurate RP-HPLC method was developed for the identification and quantification of Acetaminophen and Oxycodone using a Waters PDA-detected HPLC system. Separation was achieved on an Inertsil ODS-C18 column (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm) with a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. The mobile phase consisted of filtered and degassed Methanol and Acetonitrile in a 60:40 ratio. Detection was performed at a wavelength of 230 nm.

INTRODUCTION

Percocet® is a combination analgesic containing oxycodone and acetaminophen. Under conditions of inflammation or hyperalgesia, opioid receptors in tissues can become upregulated and transported to nerve terminals. Acetaminophen (10-11) contributes to analgesia by inhibiting the COX-1 and COX-2 isoforms of cyclooxygenase, enzymes responsible for prostaglandin (PG) synthesis. Since prostaglandins are key mediators of pain sensation, reducing their production increases the pain threshold.

Oxycodone (8-9) and its active metabolites selectively bind to the μ-opioid receptor, and to a

lesser extent the κ and δ receptors, in both the central nervous system and peripheral tissues. This interaction activates G-protein-coupled receptor signaling. Activation of μ-opioid receptors inhibits N-type voltage-operated calcium channels, reducing neurotransmitter release and thereby diminishing the perception of pain.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Preparation of Stock solution:

100 mg of Oxycodone and 100 mg of Acetaminophen API standards were accurately weighed and are transferred into two separate 100

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ml volumetric flasks, dissolved in mobile phase, then sonicated for 20 minutes to obtain 1000 μ g/ml.

Preparation of working standard solution:

From the above standard stock solution, 4 ml from each solution was transferred into 100ml volumetric flasks, made up to the volume with mobile phase to get 40 μ g/ml of Oxycodone and 40 μ g/ml of Acetaminophen.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Method validation:

Validation parameters include specificity, linearity, range, accuracy, precision, limit of detection, limit of quantification, robustness and assay (1-7).

Specificity:

Specificity is the ability to assessing equivocally the analyte in the presence of components which may be expected to be present. Typically these components include impurities, degradants, matrix etc. Blank solution and standard solutions of Oxycodone(40 μ g/ml) and Acetaminophen(40 μ g/ml) were injected into the HPLC system. The peak purity data of Oxycodone and Acetaminophen were compared. There should not be any interference at the retention time of the main peaks.

Linearity:

Linearity for the drugs Oxycodone and Acetaminophen (12-19) was determined by preparing the standard solutions at six concentrations levels in the range of 20-70 μ g/ml Oxycodone and 20-70 μ g/ml for Acetaminophen from stock solution. The linearity charts of Oxycodone and Acetaminophen was shown in the figure no 2&3. The correlation coefficient was

found to be 0.9997 and 0.9993 for Oxycodone and Acetaminophen respectively. Linearity results were tabulated in table 2.

Accuracy:

Accuracy was performed by spiking known amounts of standard solution to sample solution at three different concentrations levels (50%, 100%, 150%) and there by analyzed for %RSD which should not be more than 2.0. The % recovery was calculated and the results was reported in table no. 3 & 4.

Precision:

The precision (7-12) of the analytical method was studied by injecting six replicates of standard containing 40 μ g/ml of Oxycodone and 40 μ g/ml of Acetaminophen which were injected into HPLC system. The % RSD was calculated and the results were reported in the table no.5 & 6.

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ):

The limit of detection was defined as the concentration which yields a signal - to - noise ratio 3:1 whereas the limit of quantification was calculated to be the lowest concentration that could be measured with signal - to - noise ratio 10:1. LOD and LOQ were calculated from slope and standard deviation. The results were tabulated in table no. 7.

Robustness:

The smallest deliberate changes in method like change in flow rate are made but there were no predictable changes in the results and are in the range as per ICH guidelines. Conditions like decrease in flow rate (0.8 ml/min), increase in flow rate (1.2 ml/min) was maintained and samples were injected in duplicate manner. System

suitability parameters were not much affected and all the parameters were passed. % RSD was found to be within the limits and results were tabulated in table no. 8.

Assay:

Assay was conducted on marketed formulation and mean % assay was found. The results were tabulated in table no. 9.

Table1: Optimised Chromatographic conditions

Parameters	Method
Stationary Phase(column)	Inertsil -ODS C ₁₈ (250 x 4.6 mm, 5 μ)
Mobile Phase	Methanol and Acetonitrile (60:40)
Flow rate (ml/min)	1.0 ml/min
Run time(minutes)	8 min
Temperature in the column (°C)	Ambient
Volume of injection loop (μl)	20
Wavelength of detection (nm)	230nm
Drug RT (min)	3.570 min for Oxycodone and 5.297 for Acetaminophen.

Figure 1: Optimized chromatogram

Table 2: Linearity data of Oxycodone and Acetaminophen

Oxycodone		Acetaminophen	
Conc (μg/ml)	Peak area	Conc (μg/ml)	Peak area
20	534254	20	983353
30	775469	30	1498937
40	1025584	40	2017341
50	1275586	50	2629425
60	1567986	60	3138733
70	1817698	70	3645876

Figure 2: Calibration Curve of Oxycodone

Figure 3: Calibration Curve of Acetaminophen

Table 3: Accuracy data of Oxycodone

Concentration % of spiked level	Amount added (ppm)	Amount found (ppm)	% Recovery	Statistical Analysis of % Recovery
50% - 1	20	19.92	99.78	99.87
50% - 2	20	19.96	99.89	
50% - 3	20	19.88	99.78	0.68
100 % - 1	40	39.94	98.92	99.84
100 % - 2	40	39.86	99.75	
100% - 3	40	39.76	99.08	0.657
150% - 1	60	59.97	99.96	100.07
150% - 2	60	60.02	100.08	
150% - 3	60	60.01	100.01	0.345

Table 4: Accuracy data of Acetaminophen

Concentration % of spiked level	Amount added (ppm)	Amount found (ppm)	% Recovery	Statistical Analysis of % Recovery
50% - 1	20	19.89	99.87	99.97
50% - 2	20	19.72	99.87	
50% - 3	20	20.08	100.03	0.874
100 % - 1	40	39.92	99.88	99.97
100 % - 2	40	40.01	100.07	
100% - 3	40	40.05	100.08	0.687
150% - 1	60	59.95	98.87	99.94
150% - 2	60	59.97	99.88	
150% - 3	60	59.98	99.98	0.97

Table 5: System Precision data of Oxycodone and Acetaminophen

S. No	Peak areas of Oxycodone	Peak areas of Acetaminophen
1	1025863	2035142
2	1025642	2038624
3	1025784	2039586
4	1025537	2038867
5	1025682	2037695
Mean	1025702	2037983
SD	126.3618	1725.99
% RSD	0.01232	0.084691

Table 6: Method Precision data of Oxycodone and Acetaminophen

S. No	Peak areas of Oxycodone	Peak areas of Acetaminophen
1	1025867	2037861
2	1028965	2038967
3	1029958	2037765
4	1029685	2039685
5	1028968	2038567
6	1028567	2038868
Mean	1028668	2038619
SD	1465.087	724.713
% RSD	0.142426	0.035549

Table 7: LOD and LOQ data of Oxycodone and Acetaminophen

Drug Name	LOD ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	LOQ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
Oxycodone	0.65	1.97
Acetaminophen	0.27	0.82

Table 8: Robustness data of Oxycodone and Acetaminophen

Sr No	Drug Name	Condition	Peak area	% RSD
1	Oxycodone	Decreased Flow rate of 0.8 ml/min	1016744	0.106
2		Increased Flow rate of 1.2 ml/min	1038506	0.132
3	Acetaminophen	Decreased Flow rate of 0.8 ml/min	2026242	0.156
4		Increased Flow rate of 1.2 ml/min	2046930	0.085

Table 9: Assay data Oxycodone and Acetaminophen

Sr. No	Peak area of Oxycodone	% Assay	Peak area of Acetaminophen	% Assay
1	1025863	98.96	2035142	98.82
2	1025642		2038624	
3	1025784		2039586	
4	1025537		2038867	
5	1025682		2037695	

CONCLUSION

The developed RP-HPLC method was validated as per ICH guidelines. All the system suitability parameters were within the range as stated by ICH guidelines. Interference peaks were not observed in blank, standard and sample chromatogram. Hence simple, precise and accurate, sensitive, specific and robust method was developed and validated. This can be used in quality control department with respect to routine analysis.

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